

Model-based segmentation of long term SCADA data in the presence of heavy-tailed distributed noise with finite-variance

Hamid Shiri^{a,*}, Pawel Zimroz^a, Jacek Wodecki^a, Agnieszka Wyłomańska^b, Radosław Zimroz^a

^aFaculty of Geoen지니어ing, Mining and Geology, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Na Grobli 15, 50-421 Wrocław, Poland

^bFaculty of Pure and Applied Mathematics, Hugo Steinhaus Center, Wrocław University of Science and Technology, Wyspińskiego 27, 50-370 Wrocław, Poland

Abstract

Machinery condition prognosis systems use long-term historical data to predict the remaining useful life (RUL). One of the critical steps to reach this purpose is to segment long-term data into two or several degradation stages (healthy, unhealthy, critical stage). Finding a changing point between stages may be a crucial preliminary task for the further prediction of the degradation process. However, finding the accurate partition into two or more stages is a challenging task in the actual application when the noise inherent in the observed process exhibits non-Gaussian characteristics. In this paper, a framework for model-based segmentation is presented for the prognosis of long-term machinery data in the presence of heavy-tailed distributed noise with finite variance. It is assumed that three different stages are inherent in the degradation process and that each segment of the data follows a specific trend (constant, linear, exponential, or polynomial). At first, the data is divided into three parts. The trend functions are fitted to the data by using the robust regression method, and the cumulative error is calculated. This process is done iteratively for all possible partitions into three intervals to find the segmentation which minimizes the error. The framework has been tested via empirical analysis of the estimators of the changing points obtained in Monte Carlo simulations. Also, the discussed approaches are applied to the real data. In such measurement, the data which is commonly available (in SCADA systems) is aggregated from the raw signal and sampled at long intervals. Finally, the effectiveness of the segmentation results is assessed by comparing them with envelope frequency analysis of the raw signal to confirm the fact that the detected changing points coincide with the start time of the fault in the machine or not.

Keywords: Long-term data, Segmentation, Robust methods, Non-Gaussian noise, Changing points.

1. Introduction

Prognostics and Health Management (PHM) is one of the significant tasks in condition-based maintenance (CBM). The CBM systems are developed to assess the machine's condition by collecting massive amounts of data during the operation of machines. PHM is usually made up of four different processes [1, 2]: 1. Data acquisition is defined as the process of recording and saving different types of monitoring data from various sensors mounted on the monitored machine. 2. Construction of a health index (HI): in general, HI is defined as the set of statistical and frequency domain-based features extracted from raw signals to describe machinery's health condition. 3. Health stage (HS) evaluation and 4. Prediction of RUL. The HS evaluation is taken as an expression of fault detection in the PHM community [3]. Nevertheless, their assignments are different from each other. The diagnosis of faults is determined by the pattern and intensity of the machine fault. However, the primary purpose of the HS evaluation is to divide the continuous degradation process into several health stages due to the varying trends of HI. In addition, it is hard and undeserved to predict the RUL during a healthy stage. The RUL estimation should start from the unhealthy stage's start time, known as the first predicting time (FPT), due to the fact that in the healthy stage observations there is no valuable information about the unhealthy stage and its degradation trend. Therefore, instead of trying too hard to employ the

*hamid.shiri@pwr.edu.pl

15 complex model, such as the model with switching regimes or nonlinear trends to predict RUL, breaking the HI into
the different HS and trying to predict RUL from the last stage may be more accessible and evaluative. Commonly, for
HS evaluation, the health index is compared to a limit value that usually is provided by the manufacturer (threshold
corresponding to change from "Good Condition" (healthy stage) to "Warning" (degradation stage) and "Warning" to
"Alarm" stage (critical stage). Unfortunately, we do not know the limit values or desired lifetime in many cases, which
20 is often present in the raw materials industry [4], especially when the machine is unique. Also, it should be noted that
most of these thresholds are introduced by manufacturing industries and are defined based on particular working and
environmental conditions standards that may not be valid when the conditions change.

In recent years, several papers have been published in the literature to detect changing points in time series in
different areas such as financial, medical and meteorology [5–14]. Also, it should be noted that this process is known
25 as regime-switching point detection or signal segmentation in other communities. Signal segmentation is repeatedly
employed in signal processing applications to separate original data into homogeneous segments or extract the pattern.
Gasior et al. [15] utilized segmentation for shock extraction in sieving screen vibrations. Kucharczyk et al. [16] used
stochastic modelling for seismic signal segmentation. Grzesiek et al. [17] proposed a methodology to detect regime
change when regime A smoothly transforms into regime B. Also, a few papers have been published in the PHM
30 community based on dividing HI into different HS. Some of these articles divide HI into two different stages. Alkan
et al. [18] presented a methodology for the diagnosis of electromechanical systems faults based on the variance-sensitive
adaptive alarm threshold and principal component analysis (PCA). Fink et al. [19] explained the prediction of RUL
as a two-stage classification to detect the machine's condition after the defined time interval. Schlechtingen et al.
[20] compared three different model-based approaches for the two-stage division of wind turbines, i.e., a regression-
35 based model and two artificial neural networks (ANN) based models. Hu et al. [21] used a one-class support vector
machine and a Gaussian threshold model for condition monitoring of the turbo-pumps. The two-stage division is
valuable only for cases where the degradation trends of machinery in the unhealthy stage are consistent and can
be represented utilizing a single degradation model. Nonetheless, due to variations of fault patterns or operational
conditions, the degradation trends of machinery may change. According to this circumstance, the unhealthy stage
40 should be split into various stages based on the different degradation trends. A few of these research divided HI and
spectra into several stages, with changing points detection approaches. For instance, Kimotho et al. [22] segmented
the degradation trend into five stages due to variation of frequency amplitude in power spectra density. Sutrisno
et al. [23] split the bearing degradation process into different stages by employing anomaly detection of frequency
spectra. Hu et al. [24], separated the HI into four stages using changing points of confidence levels. Methods based
45 on machine learning techniques are frequently used for long-term data analysis for classification, fault detection,
prognosis, etc. [4, 25–31]. In this case, unsupervised classification, i.e. clustering, is required because every machine
works under different conditions and labeling data is not an easy task. Hence, the clustering approach has a huge
potential to divide long-term data into several regimes. The authors of [26] proposed the Long Short Term Memory
(LSTM) network with the clustering method for multi-stage predicting RUL. Jaskaran Singh et al. [27] introduced an
50 adaptive data-driven model-based approach to detect regime-changing points using K-means clustering. Also, discrete
state transition models such as HMMs [32–37] and dynamic state-space models [38, 39] are frequently employed to
segment degradation processes into multiple stages. However, most of the mentioned research was performed under
the assumption that observation noise has Gaussian distribution, while in most actual applications, especially in the
PHM area it is not a proper assumption. In many cases, the impulsive noise can be observed, which is properly
55 described with a heavy-tailed distribution, meaning that the marginal events are likely to occur. This may happen for
several reasons. Wind inflows are one of the possible sources of impulsive noise in wind turbine [40–42], the ore
falling on devices in the mining environment is another [43, 44].

Due to the specific random character of the degradation process observed in the HI data, classical algorithms
known from the literature may fail to properly perform the segmentation procedure [45–47]. To solve this issue,
60 in the paper, we propose the model-based approach according to historical data to robustly identify the border of the
stages (healthy/degradation/critical stage) when the machine changes the condition in the presence of non-Gaussian
noise with finite variance. It is considered that the degradation process is composed of three stages and each stage of
the data follows a specific trend (constant, linear and exponential or polynomial). First, the long-term historical data
is divided into three parts. The trend functions are fitted to the data using the regression method and the cumulative
65 error is calculated. This process is done iteratively for all possible partitions into three intervals to find the changing
points, which minimizes the error. This procedure is repeated using different regression methods including robust

70 methods such as the least absolute error and fitting the Student's t-distribution. It should be noted that, the Student's t-distribution was chosen because it is both heavy-tailed (unlike Gaussian distribution) and at the same time has finite variance (for the considered range of degree of freedom) making it easier to fit than some other theoretically well established distributions. Also, in our previous paper we showed that this distribution can describe a random part as proper [48]. Furthermore, for better comparison and to check if the non-Gaussian noise assumption is necessary, along with the mentioned approach we have included two hidden Markov model based methods having the Gaussian noise assumption (These two methods use a relatively different structure for segmentation). We also presented a waterfall plot of the short-time envelope spectrum calculated for available raw vibration data for the real data sets. Such a 3D
75 plot demonstrates how the envelope spectrum changes and allow us to visually validate that detected changing points are coinciding with the time the fault in the machine occurs or not.

The paper is structured as follows: after the introduction, in Section 2, we reviewed the most common long-term data model and described the model used in this paper. In Section 3, we have reviewed the theoretical and mathematical aspects of the methods used in this paper. In Section 4, we generated data based on Section 2 and employed the proposed structure to segment long-term data in the presence of Gaussian and non-Gaussian noise.
80 Finally, in Section 5 the results of applying the proposed approach to three benchmark data sets are presented with an indication of all intermediate steps, and in Section 6 the conclusions are formed.

2. Long term data model

Model-based degradation process analysis is a common approach in the PHM community. These models can
85 be described by various deterministic trends (linear, polynomial, exponential and constant), see Fig.1, various noise distributions, and structures of dependence for random components; see Fig. 2, 3.

According to the pre-knowledge of the degradation process, the model can be selected; for example, the linear model is frequently used for describing the drilling degradation process [1, 49], see panel (b) Fig. 1. Meanwhile, the exponential degradation trend is usually used for expressing the battery degradation process [50–52] (but with a negative slope), see panel (c) in Fig.1. To describe the degradation process of bearings, gears or shafts, different kinds
90 of models composed from various deterministic trends may be used [53, 54] (see Fig. 1, panel (d), (e), (f)).

In this paper, we assume that the degradation process has complex trends, such as those presented in Fig. 3. This model consists of three stages. At first the degradation process is centered around some constant level which correspond to the healthy stage. The second stage is described with a linear function corresponding to the degradation stage. The last part has either an exponential or a polynomial trend that is referred to as the critical stage. The two
95 moments of the transition from one stage to another we will denote as changing points: CP1 (is a border between the healthy stage with constant trend and degradation stage with linear trend) and CP2 (is a border between the degradation stage with linear trend and critical stage with exponential or polynomial trend).

Also, this model can include different kinds of noise distribution covering the degradation process. In most of the
100 research in this area, it is assumed the distribution of the noise is Gaussian, see Fig. 2 [55], while this assumption is not proper when the machine works in harsh environments [48]. To achieve a model that better reflects the real condition, in our previous work [48] we developed a simulation framework that produces degradation process observations; an exemplary trajectory is shown in Fig.3. In this framework along with the trend of the degradation process, the distribution of the noise and its scale (square root of the variance in the Gaussian case) are also changing in each
105 stage. The main characteristics of our framework is summarised in Table 1. In this paper, we assume of finite variance for non-Gaussian distribution.

Figure 1: Different types of HI variations and degradation models: (a) good condition (constant trend), (b) good to gradual wear (linear trend), (c) exponential trend, (d) good to accelerated wear (linear trend), (e) good to accelerated wear (exponential trend), (f) three stages model (good, linear progress and exponential(polynomial) progress of degradation) [48].

Figure 2: Three stage degradation model [56].

Figure 3: The proposed long term degradation model with 3 stages [48].

Table 1: Main characteristics of the data for the three stages indicated in Fig. 3. [48].

	stage 1	stage 2	stage 3
Trend	constant	linear	exponential or polynomial
Scale	nearly constant	linearly growing	lin. or exp. growing
Random component	Gaussian/non-Gaussian	Gaussian/non-Gaussian	Gaussian/non-Gaussian

3. Methodology

We assume that the long-term health index (HI) data are composed of three distinct stages that expose significantly different behaviors. Based on this assumption, our aim is to divide the time series into these three sections by using robust mathematical regression methods, achieving best fitting to one of the specified models. All of the methods that we discuss assume that the health index is a stochastic process (its observations we denote by X_t where t is the discrete-time index) and that its trend is a function of time and a set of parameters. Thus, the HI observation process consists of the time-changing trend (expected value of X_t , which we assume to be finite) and residual r_t , hence we have:

$$X_t = \widehat{X}_t + r_t, \quad \widehat{X}_t = EX_t. \quad (1)$$

As Θ in this section we denote the complete set of parameters to be fitted to the data. It may include the changing points (see previous section) and the parameters of a probability distribution if a method employs any. Both terms on the right-hand side of Eq. (1) depend on Θ . We now present the methods in two groups.

3.1. Piece-wise regression models

This class of methods allows to divide data into three segments, each having different form of the model. We employ three functional components: constant, linear, and exponential as below:

$$\widehat{X}_t(\Theta) = \begin{cases} f_1(t, \theta_1) = \theta_1, & 0 < t \leq \tau_1, \\ f_2(t, \theta_2, \theta_3) = \theta_2 t + \theta_3, & \tau_1 < t \leq \tau_2, \\ f_3(t, \theta_4, \theta_5, \theta_6) = \theta_4 \exp(\theta_5 t) + \theta_6, & \tau_2 < t \leq N, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where the variables τ_1 and τ_2 stand for CP1 and CP2, the number N is signal length, and $\theta_1, \dots, \theta_6$ are constants (which need to be fitted) parameters used to model deterministic parts of the HI.

3.1.1. Ordinary least squares (OLS)

The most basic approach is based on minimizing the sum of squares of the residuals of the model. The procedure designed to find an optimal set of parameters iterates in two loops through possible divisions into three windows (which allows us to find optimal τ_1 and τ_2).

$$\widehat{\Theta} = \underset{\Theta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{t=1}^{\tau_1-1} (X_t - f_1(t, \theta_1))^2 + \sum_{t=\tau_1}^{\tau_2-1} (X_t - f_2(t, \theta_2, \theta_3))^2 + \sum_{t=\tau_2}^N (X_t - f_3(t, \theta_4, \theta_5, \theta_6))^2. \quad (3)$$

In the case of observations with Gaussian noise, given each division, optimal parameters can be equivalently estimated using Maximum Likelihood Estimation (MLE) with Gaussian distributed residuals.

3.1.2. Dynamic programming segmentation

In this method the optimal segmentation of the time-series of the observations $X_{t=1, \dots, N}$ is done by fitting the model parameters in terms of Gaussian distribution MLE by using optimized dynamic programming. The computation cost of this model is high based on using dynamic programming. For more details on this method, please see the following references [57, 58].

3.1.3. Iteratively reweighted least squares (IRLS)

The method of iteratively reweighted least squares (IRLS) is a modification of the OLS method where the weights are assigned to the error terms according to changing variance which we assume to be finite (for each time t the weight $w_t = 1/\sigma_t$ is reciprocal of the corresponding standard deviation σ_t of the error term of the observation). The weights are modified in an iterative way; thus, in the j -th step, the vector of weights $w_t^{(j)}$, $t = 1, \dots, N$ is applied, which results in updating the piecewise regression parameters:

$$\widehat{\Theta}^{(j)} = \underset{\Theta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{t=1}^{\tau_1-1} w_t^{(j)} (X_t - f_1(t, \theta_1^{(j-1)}))^2 + \sum_{t=\tau_1}^{\tau_2-1} w_t^{(j)} (X_t - f_2(t, \theta_2^{(j-1)}, \theta_3^{(j-1)}))^2 + \sum_{t=\tau_2}^N w_t^{(j)} (X_t - f_3(t, \theta_4^{(j-1)}, \theta_5^{(j-1)}, \theta_6^{(j-1)}))^2, \quad (4)$$

where $\widehat{\Theta}^{(j)}$ is the current values set of Θ in the j -th iteration of the IRLS algorithm. Among many different iterative methods of finding the proper weights, we used a method applying to the residuals of the model the Tukey biweight function $\phi(x) = x(1 - x^2)^2$ (as defined in [59]) implemented in Matlab `robustfit()` function. The weights are updated using the formula [60]:

$$w_t^{(j)} = \frac{\phi(\varepsilon_t^{(j)})}{\varepsilon_t^{(j)}}, \quad (5)$$

where $\varepsilon_t^{(j)}$ is the residual of the model divided by the current estimate of the standard deviation term, that is:

$$\varepsilon_t^{(j)} = \frac{r_t}{\sigma_t^{(j)}}. \quad (6)$$

3.1.4. Least absolute error (LAE)

The sum of absolute deviations is used as a cost function instead of a sum of squares. It is a widely known alternative to the OLS method, making the fitting of the regression parameters more robust, even in the case of infinite variance [61]. The optimization procedure including LAE cost function with changing points is defined as follows:

$$\widehat{\Theta} = \underset{\Theta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{t=1}^{\tau_1-1} |X_t - f_1(t, \theta_1)| + \sum_{t=\tau_1}^{\tau_2-1} |X_t - f_2(t, \theta_2, \theta_3)| + \sum_{t=\tau_2}^N |X_t - f_3(t, \theta_4, \theta_5, \theta_6)|. \quad (7)$$

The same as in the OLS method we iterate through all the possible divisions into three stages and in that way we find τ_1 and τ_2 . This method is beneficial when the errors have rather a heavy-tailed than Gaussian distribution. Namely given each division into three windows, it can be equivalently stated as applying MLE estimation with Laplace distributed residuals.

3.1.5. Student's t-distribution estimation (ST)

In this method, the residuals of the model in each degradation stage are assumed to have a scaled Student's t distribution, that is:

$$r_t = \begin{cases} \sigma_1 u_t, & 0 < t \leq \tau_1, \\ \sigma_2 u_t, & \tau_1 < t \leq \tau_2, \\ \sigma_3 u_t, & \tau_2 < t \leq N, \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $\{u_t\}_{t=1, \dots, N}$ is a series of independent random variables from the Student's t distribution with ν_i degrees of freedom for the i -th segment ($i = 1, 2, 3$). This enables the heavy tails in the error distribution and makes the fitting more robust allowing proper parametrization of the non-Gaussian observation data. The estimation procedure is based on MLE technique applied to each possible division into three stages. The optimal set of parameters is found to fulfill the following:

$$\widehat{\Theta} = \underset{\Theta}{\operatorname{argmin}} \sum_{t=1}^{\tau_1-1} \log \left(p_{\nu_1} \left(\frac{X_t - f_1(t, \theta_1)}{\sigma_1} \right) \right) + \sum_{t=\tau_1}^{\tau_2-1} \log \left(p_{\nu_2} \left(\frac{X_t - f_2(t, \theta_2, \theta_3)}{\sigma_2} \right) \right) + \sum_{t=\tau_2}^N \log \left(p_{\nu_3} \left(\frac{X_t - f_3(t, \theta_4, \theta_5, \theta_6)}{\sigma_3} \right) \right), \quad (9)$$

where $p_{\nu}(\cdot)$ is the probability density function (PDF) of the Student's t-distribution given by the formula [62]:

$$p_{\nu}(y) = \frac{(1 + \frac{y^2}{\nu})^{-\frac{\nu+1}{2}}}{B(\frac{\nu}{2}, \frac{1}{2}) \sqrt{\nu}}, \quad y \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (10)$$

where $B(\cdot, \cdot)$ is the beta function. The parameter ν is called the number of the degrees of freedom. We restrict the parameter ν to be greater than 2, thus the variance of the underlying random variable is finite [62].

3.2. Hidden Markov models and Expectation-Maximization algorithm

For a shorter notation, in this subsection, we will denote the process of the observations as $X = \{X_t\}_{t=1, \dots, N}$. Hidden Markov models are the models in which to describe the evolution of the observations process X , an additional unobserved process (hidden states) $z = \{z_t\}_{t=1, \dots, N}$ is introduced so that the whole system has the Markov property. As the hidden states are unknown, the full likelihood of a system $P(X, z|\Theta)$ cannot be calculated directly to obtain the parameters with the MLE method. The standard iterative method that can be used instead is called Expectation-Maximization (EM) algorithm. First, some initial values of $\Theta^{(0)}$ are set. Next, the procedure of EM is based on repeated steps of calculating the expectation of the likelihood given the distribution of z conditioned with X and $\Theta = \Theta^{(u)}$ and reassigning Θ to new values that maximize the conditional expectation. The u -th step can be described with the updating formula:

$$\Theta^{(u+1)} = \underset{\Theta}{\operatorname{argmax}} E_{z|X, \Theta = \Theta^{(u)}} \left(P(X, z|\Theta) \right), \quad (11)$$

where the letter E stands for the conditional expectation. We consider two different models from this class. However, they share the same equation for the evolution of X given z , which is a polynomial regression (of degree p):

$$X_t = \sum_{i=0}^p \beta_{i, z_k} t^i + \sigma_{z_t} \varepsilon_t, \quad (12)$$

where $t = 1, \dots, N$, the constants β_{0, z_k} to β_{p, z_k} are polynomial coefficients in the state (degradation stage) z_k , and ε_t is Gaussian white noise. The set of $p + 1$ polynomial coefficients depends on the current stage z_t . Hidden states may be interpreted as the degradation stages indexed from 1 to K in the proper order from the healthy state to the complete degradation (so K denotes the number of distinct degradation stages). In this paper according to the framework described in Section 2 we put $K=3$.

In the HMM approach, CP1 and CP2 are not included in Θ . The result of fitting the HMM model to the data contains the probabilities for each t of the current stage z_t being equal to $1, \dots, K$. The state with the highest probability indicates in which degradation state the observed machine is at time t , and thus we obtain the division of the degradation process into three stages.

185 **3.2.1. Hidden Markov model regression (HMMR)**

This approach employs a mixture of polynomial regressions handled by hidden states of a discrete-time Markov chain. Changing of the stages is therefore fully described by the initial distribution and the one-step transition matrix. A significant restrictions are therefore put to the transition probabilities to better reflect the nature of the process, thus for all $l = 1, \dots, K$ we have:

$$P(z_{t+1} = k | z_t = l) = 0, \quad \text{for } k \notin \{l, l + 1\} \quad (13)$$

190 and generally nonzero otherwise. The parameters are estimated through the Baum-Welch algorithm as described in [57].

3.2.2. Hidden logistic process (HLP)

In this method, the process of the unobserved switching stages that affects the set of polynomial regression coefficients is modeled with a multinomial logistic regression model. The distribution of the current stage z_t in this model is assumed to be as follows:

$$\pi_{t,k}(\beta) = P(z_t = k | \beta) = \frac{\exp(\sum_{i=0}^p \beta_{ki} t^i)}{\sum_{l=1}^K \exp(\sum_{i=0}^p \beta_{li} t^i)}, \quad \text{for } k = 1, \dots, K, \quad (14)$$

where $\beta = [\beta_{ki}]_{k=1, \dots, K, i=0, \dots, p}$ is the matrix containing $p + 1$ regression parameters for all K degradation stages. As z is not observed, the total log-likelihood of the model must include the Gaussian distribution of X_t given z_t . In terms of probability density functions, we have (see [57]):

$$p(X | \Theta) = \sum_{t=1}^N \log \sum_{k=1}^K \pi_{t,k}(\beta) p_{\Theta}(X_t | z_t = k), \quad (15)$$

200 where the Gaussian PDF denoted with $p_{\Theta}(X_t | z_t = k)$ comes from Eq. (12). The resulting model is a special case of the time-heterogeneous Gaussian mixture model. A dedicated EM for this approach is described in [57]. As is shown there, in a single iteration of EM, the expectation term which is a function of Θ (compare Eq. (11)) can be separated into two terms, one dependent on β and the other dependent on σ and β . Thus, fitting of these two sets of parameters can be done independently. The matrix β is estimated utilizing a multi-class iterative reweighted least squares (IRLS) approach.

205 **4. Analysis of simulated data**

Based on the assumption of Section 2, the long-term data model is used to generate HI observations. After the mentioned methodologies are employed to segment the data into three stages in the presence of Gaussian noise and non-Gaussian noise. Additionally, to show the performance of the methodology, the results were compared together.

4.1. Model description

210 Considering the model discussed in Section 2, we propose the following model for generating $HI(t)$ that will be used in simulation study:

$$HI(t) = R(t) + D(t), \quad (16)$$

where $R(t)$ and $D(t)$ are, respectively, random and deterministic components. Both these parts consist of three stages, denoted as stage 1, stage 2 and stage 3, which are related to three considered underlying stages (healthy stage/degradation stage/critical stage) and determine the behavior of the process with regard to both trend and noise's scale (variance in Gaussian distribution). Let us assume that we have a sample signal $HI(1), \dots, HI(N)$. The changing point between stages 1 and 2 is denoted as τ_1 , and the changing point between stages 2 and 3 by τ_2 , where $1 < \tau_1 < \tau_2 < N$. In other words, we can divide the signal segment by segment, so that the sequence $HI(1), \dots, HI(\tau_1)$ corresponds to stage 1, the sequence $HI(\tau_1 + 1), \dots, HI(\tau_2)$ corresponds to stage 2 and the sequence $HI(\tau_2 + 1), \dots, HI(N)$ corresponds to stage 3.

220 In the simulation study presented in the next section, we assume two distributions for the random component, namely Gaussian and Student's t. The aim of using both Gaussian and Student's t (being an example of a heavy-tailed distribution) in the simulation is to provide a comparison between them for condition monitoring application, as non-Gaussian behavior is widely present in real scenarios. The random component corresponding to $R(t)$ is constructed in the following way:

$$R(t) = SC(t)\widetilde{R}(t), \quad (17)$$

225 where the function $SC(t)$ represents the time-changing scale and $\widetilde{R}(t)$ is a series of independent identically distributed random variables. For the Gaussian distribution, for each t we put $\widetilde{R}(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$ and for the Student's t distribution case $\widetilde{R}(t) \sim t(\nu)$. For simplicity, we assume that the distribution in each stage is the same, however, as it was mentioned in Section 2, in practice, it may be different for different stages.

230 As it was mentioned, its behavior is different for each stage, namely, we assume that in stage 1 the scale grows linearly, from σ_1 to σ_2 (where both values are relatively close to each other), then in stage 2 it also increases linearly, from σ_2 to σ_3 , and finally, in stage 3 it grows exponentially, from σ_3 to σ_4 . The function $SC(t)$ is defined as follows:

$$SC(t) = \begin{cases} a_1 t + b_1 & 0 < t \leq \tau_1, \\ a_2 t + b_2 & \tau_1 < t \leq \tau_2, \\ a_3 \exp(b_3 t) & \tau_2 < t \leq N, \end{cases} \quad (18)$$

where constants $a_1, b_1, a_2, b_2, a_3, b_3$ are derived in such a way that $SC(1) = \sigma_1$, $SC(\tau_1) = \sigma_2$, $SC(\tau_2) = \sigma_3$ and $SC(N) = \sigma_4$ [48].

235 The behavior of the deterministic component $D(t)$ in Eq. (16) has different nature for different stages. Let us recall that in the stage 1 it is at the fixed constant level, denoted here as c_1 . Then, in stages 2 and 3 we consider linear and exponential functions, respectively, with the same growth parameters as for the corresponding stages of the scale function $SC(t)$. Moreover, we assume the function $D(t)$ has no discontinuities in the stage changing points τ_1 and τ_2 . Under these assumptions, the deterministic term of the signal has the form

$$D(t) = \begin{cases} c_1 & 0 < t \leq \tau_1, \\ a_2 t + c_2 & \tau_1 < t \leq \tau_2, \\ a_3 \exp(b_3 t) + c_3 & \tau_2 < t \leq N, \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

240 where c_2 and c_3 are derived in such a way that $D(t)$ is a continuous function. In panel (a) in Fig. 4 we present the deterministic component $D(t)$ and the scale function $SC(t)$ for the following values of the parameters: $\tau_1 = 1000$, $\tau_2 = 1600$, $N = 1700$, $\sigma_1 = 1$, $\sigma_2 = 2$, $\sigma_3 = 7$, $\sigma_4 = 25$ and $c_1 = 10$. Here, we assumed four additional values of the ν - parameter, namely $\nu \in \{2.1, 3, 5, 10\}$. As can be seen, for the Gaussian distributed signal we do not observe the outlying observations; see panel (b) in Fig. 4, while for the non-Gaussian heavy-tailed case, large impulses occur in the data, see panel (c) in Fig. 4. The smaller the ν , the higher impulses may occur in the signal.

245 It should be noted that the model used for the simulation is different from the one used in the segmentation methods. A model used for piecewise regression methods (see Eq. (2)) is a simplified version of the simulated model presented in this section neglecting the scaling factor $SC(t)$, i.e. changing it to a constant. The reason of such is to investigate how complex behaviour may be modeled with a simplified approach.

Figure 4: Simulation Model: (a) deterministic part with marked changing points, (b) Gaussian noise, (c) non-Gaussian noise with $\nu = 3$, (d) health index in presence of Gaussian noise, (e) health index in presence of non-Gaussian noise.

4.2. Analysis for Gaussian noise

250 In this subsection, the proposed methodology is applied to data generated by the proposed model assuming that the noise term has Gaussian distribution $\tilde{R}(t) \sim \mathcal{N}(0, 1)$. The results of the segmentation to the simulated data are presented together for all of the selected methods. Due to the simulation procedure at Time=1000, the healthy stage is going to the degradation stage CP1(which is take meaning of τ_1), and Time=1600 is CP2 (which is take meaning of τ_2).

255 In Fig. 5 we can observe an exemplary simulated trajectory along with the estimated changing points CP1 and CP2 resulting from each of the methods. As we can see, for this case, where all stages include Gaussian noise, the selected methods could detect the CP1 with good precision. CP1 is detected by most of the methods such as ST, LAE, and IRLS precisely, while the rest of the methods also discovered this point somewhere around Time=1000 and Time=1088, which is acceptable except HLP method that discovered this point at Time=882 that happens earlier than expected time. According to this fact, the transition between the two last stages is significant; CP2 was found with most methods, except IRLS, OLS and HLP, which could not detect this point as an appropriate point.

Figure 5: Changing points detection in the presence of a Gaussian noise.

The estimation procedure was repeated for 100 simulations from the same model. In Fig. 6 the estimation results are visualized using box plots. The vertical length of the blue boxes corresponds to IQR (an inter-quartile range which is the range between Q1 and Q3). In addition, outliers can be observed. The estimation of CP1 and CP2, according to HMMR, HLP and DPS, has low variance (it can be inferred from the small value of IQR); however, in the case of CP1, the result is biased to the right from the true value of 1000. In the case of CP2 most of the methods (excluding IRLS, OLS and ST) tend to have a significant number of outliers on the left side from the true value of 1600.

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Figure 6: Monte Carlo analysis for changing point detection in presence of Gaussian noise.

Also, the mean square error (MSE) is calculated based on real changing points (CP1=1000 and CP2=1600) for all Monte Carlo simulations and illustrated in Fig.7. As can be seen in this Fig.7, the IRLS method has the lowest MSE for detecting CP1, while it has the highest MSE for detecting CP2. Also, the TS method could detect CP2 very well. However, it has not been able to perform as well as CP2 in detecting CP1. By comparing all the bars, it can be concluded that the DPS, HMMR, and ST methods perform lowest MSE in the case of Gaussian noise.

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Figure 7: MSE for Monte Carlo analysis for changing point detection in presence of Gaussian noise.

4.3. Analysis for non-Gaussian noise

In this part, the proposed methodology is applied to data generated by the proposed model with student's t -distributed random component, considering different values of the parameter ν varying from the two marginal: value closely above 2 which is the limit case below which the variance become infinite (highly non-Gaussian) and value big enough so that the distribution is close to Gaussian.

According to the simulation procedure, CP1 and CP2 are equal to Time=1000 and Time=1600, respectively. In Fig.8 we can observe an exemplary simulated trajectory along with the estimated changing points CP1 and CP2 resulting from each of the methods for the case of degrees of freedom $\nu = 2.1$. CP1 is discovered by methods such as ST and LAE precisely, while the rest of the methods could not correctly identify this point; for example, The HMMR, DPS, IRLS, and HLP discover this point at Time = 347, 348, 600, and 900, respectively; also, OLS detected this point with a delay at Time=1280. Similarly, ST and LAE precisely detected CP2, and HMMR and DPS discovered this point with a slight delay at Time=1612, which is acceptable, while IRLS on OLS identified this point at Time =1400 and 1440, which is very early, and the results of HLP are not valuable.

Figure 8: Segmentation results for non-Gaussian simulation case with $\nu = 2.1$.

To confirm the efficacy of the methods, the estimation procedure was repeated for 100 simulations from the same model for different levels of non-Gaussian noise. In Fig. 9 the estimation results are visualized using box plots. By analysing the box plot, as we expect, it can be seen obviously the ST method has best performance in detecting both changing points(particularly CP2) in presence of different non-Gaussian noise level.

Figure 9: Monte Carlo analysis for changing point detection in the presence of different levels of non-Gaussian noise, (a) $\nu = 2.1$, (b) $\nu = 3$, (c) $\nu = 5$, (d) $\nu = 10$.

290 Also, the mean square error (MSE) is calculated based on real changing points (CP1=1000 and CP2=1600) for all
 Monte Carlo simulations for different values of ν and shown in Fig.10. As can be seen in panel (a) of Fig.10, MSE of
 many mentioned methods applied to detect CP1, such as OLS, HMMR, DPS, and more or less HLP, has increased by
 decreasing the ν value (by decreasing ν the impulsiveness is increased). However, the reduction of the ν value does
 not have a particular effect on the MSE of the robust method such as ST, LAE, and IRLS. Also, it should be mentioned
 295 that ST, IRLS, and HLP have the lowest MSE for detecting CP1 among all the methods mentioned. Likewise, the
 MSE of methods for CP2 is shown in panel (b) of Fig.10. The MSE of methods such as HMMR, DPS, and more or
 less OLS increases as ν decreases, while the MSE of methods such as ST, LAE, IRLS, and more or less HLP is not
 affected by the decreasing value of ν . Furthermore, the ST method could detect CP2 with the lowest MSE among all
 methods.

Figure 10: MSE for Monte Carlo analysis for changing point detection in the presence of different levels of non-Gaussian noise, (a) bar plot of MSE for CP1, (b) bar plot of MSE for CP2.

300 5. Real data analysis

In this section, we apply and evaluate the proposed methodology for available real data sets. These data are typically employed as benchmark data sets for different papers and competitions and have specific behavior corresponding to noise properties and deterministic trends. In the following sections, essential information about objects, experiments, and data will be recalled, and appropriate references are provided.

305 5.1. IMS data Set

This data set was collected by the Intelligent Maintenance System (IMS) laboratory of the University of Cincinnati. The IMS data set included three subsets of bearing degradation tests. Four Rexnord ZA-2115 double row bearings were used on a shaft during the degradation tests Fig. 11. Accelerometers were mounted on the bearing housings. At the end of the test, degradation patterns are recorded in detail by checking the bearings. The bearings in the IMS data set have a longer and more complicated degradation trend than other benchmark data sets. In some cases, the 'increase-decrease-increase' behavior can also be observed in bearing degradation trends related to the 'self-healing' nature of damage phenomena. Furthermore, this data set has enough frequency resolution of the vibration signals for extracting frequency domain features to monitor the degradation bearing process and frequency analysis for condition monitoring. According to data set documentation, each file consists of 20,480 data samples with a sampling frequency of 20 kHz. Furthermore, this data set has been analyzed in many publications for segmentation [35, 63], RUL prediction [64–68] and condition monitoring [69].

To apply our proposed methodology to the IMS data set, data set number 2 is selected as a case study. This data set was collected from February 12, 2004, 10:32:39 to February 19, 2004, 06:22:39 and include 984 sets of recorded vibration data. Every of these vibration sets is recorded for 1 second with a 20 kHz sampling rate, and this procedure is repeated every 10 minutes panel (a) in Fig. 12. Also, in this study, the RMS of each vibration set is employed as HI to following degradation procedure see panel (b) in Fig. 12. As shown in panel (b) in Fig. 12 at the beginning of the degradation process, the vibration amplitude increased due to the impact generated by the initial surface defect, such as cracks or spalling. Then the impact amplitude decreased because the initial surface defect was smoothed by continuous rolling contact. When the damage is spread over a broader area, the vibration amplitude increases again.

Figure 11: IMS test rig.

Figure 12: IMS data set case number 2, (a) raw bearing run-to-failure vibration signals, (b) health index (RMS).

325 5.2. FEMTO data set

The FEMTO data set was acquired by Franche-Comté Electronics Mechanics Thermal Science and Optics– Sciences and Technologies institute from a PRONOSTIA platform, Fig. 13. This data set includes 17 historical records that show bearing degradation. Two accelerometers and a temperature sensor are used to acquire acceleration and temperature. Additionally, the speed of the shaft was kept stable during the test. In this data set, the bearing failure pattern and the bearing degradation trend are different under the same operating condition. Furthermore, the sampling

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Figure 13: FEMTO test rig.

frequency of the data set is 25600 Hz, but the length of the signal is 0.1 second, so it is too low for standard frequency analysis and spectrogram. Similarly to the IMS data set, this data set has been employed in many publications for health index construction [70–77], segmentation of degradation process [22, 78–81] and RUL prediction [82–87].

335 Bearing1 – 1 is selected as a case study in this research from the FEMTO data set. This data set includes 2803 sets of recorded vibration data. Each of these vibration sets is recorded for 0.1 seconds with a 25.6 kHz sampling rate (see panel (a) in Fig. 14). This process is repeated every 10 seconds. The shaft speed is approximately 1800 rpm and the load is equal to 4000 N. Also, in this study, the RMS of each vibration set is employed as HI, see panel (b) in Fig.14.

Figure 14: FEMTO data set case number 1, (a) Raw bearing run-to-failure vibration signals, (b) health index (RMS).

5.3. Wind turbine data set

340 This data set is collected from a wind turbine (see Fig 15). The sensor has been mounted on a high-speed bearing shaft of the 2.2 MW power wind turbine. This data set was acquired over more than 50 days using two different ways. In the first approach, the raw vibration signal is acquired for 6 seconds with a sampling frequency of 100000 Hz per day for +50 days (see panel (a) in Fig.16) and for the second version, the inner race energy of the bearing is calculated every 10 min for +50 days (see panel (b) in Fig. 16). For more information on the methodology used to calculate the inner race energy, see [88].

In the end, the inner race fault has occurred, which has been proven by inspection, see Fig 15. The bearing type used during the test is 32222 – J2- SKF. It should be mentioned that this data set has been used for prognosis by several papers [88–91].

Figure 15: Wind turbine test rigs.

Figure 16: Wind turbine data set, (a) raw bearing run-to-failure vibration signals, (b) health index (Inner race energy).

5.4. Results and discussion

In this subsection, we presented the results of our proposed methodology for three real data sets (IMS, FEMTO, and wind turbine data set). We apply our robust approach to every data set and compare the results with conventional methods.

5.4.1. Results for IMS data set

The results of the segmentation methods for this case study are presented in panel (a) of Fig. 17. As it can be seen in panel (a) of Fig. 17, most of the methods detected the first changing point (CP1) (the boundary point between the healthy stage and degradation stage) between Time=500 and 560. By visual check of the HI and results, it looks like most of the methods performed the proper results. For the second changing point (the boundary point between degradation stage and critical stage trend) plenty of methods such as OLS, HMMR, DPS, IRLS, and HLP method detected this point around Time=700, where indeed HI presents a big increase of value. In comparison, the LAE and ST methods detected Time=800 and 900 as CP2, respectively. By visually checking the trend of HI, it can be concluded that the result of the LAE and ST method is closer to reality for detecting the second changing point CP2. However, to confirm our results, the envelope analysis is applied for each vibration set, and the result is sequentially plotted in panel (b) of Fig. 17. For more details about envelope analysis we refer to [92–95].

As can be seen in panel (b) of Fig. 17 after Time=527 harmonic frequency has appeared, which means the bearing went to the degradation stage. By comparison of the envelope analysis and segmentation methods, it can be concluded that ST and HLP methods provide the best result.

Figure 17: Changing points detection IMS data set case number 2, (a) result of changing points detection method, (b) envelope spectrum of the raw vibration signal.

5.4.2. Results for FEMTO data set

The results of the segmentation methods for this case study are presented in Fig.18. As can be seen, this data set perfectly follows the idea of 3 stages: for Time= 0 to c.a. 1300 it is nearly flat, then up to Time=2700 it is linear increase and then rapid growth occurs. Some noise, especially in the middle stage, is seen, and some minor outliers can also be noticed. Thus, we consider it to be a trend with nearly Gaussian noise. As shown in Fig. 18 most of the algorithms detected the first changing point (boundary point between healthy and degradation stage) between Time=1200 and 1400, except HMM-based algorithms such as HMMR and HLP that discovered the first changing point much later than it occurs in reality. Based on the visual check first changing point should be located around Time=1300. This means that the ST method could detect this point as well. It should be considered that transferring between the healthy and degradation stages is smooth, and it is not easy to detect this point. According to Fig. 18 the second changing point should be somewhere around Time=2700. Therefore, it can be concluded that the ST, LAE, OLS, HMMR, and HLP methods could detect this point as well. However, DPS and IRLS methods have not been able to discover this point properly.

Figure 18: Result of changing points detection methods for the FEMTO data set.

5.4.3. Results for wind turbine data set

To apply the proposed approach to the wind turbine data set, inner race energy is selected as a health index. As can be seen in panel (b) of Fig. 16 this data set includes many outliers. Thus, we consider it as a trend with non-Gaussian noise. In addition, a few fluctuations have appeared on HI may that have corresponded to the variation of the load or some phenomena like self-healing. This specific behavior in real cases makes a significant challenge to the segmentation and prediction of RUL. In Fig. 19 the results of the segmentation methods for this case study are presented. The CP1 (changing point between the healthy stage and degradation stage) is detected by all methods somewhere between 15 March and 21 March; for instance, OLS, ST, LAE, and IRLS discovered this point on 15 March, while HMMR, DPS, and HLP detected this point on 18 March, 18 March and 19 March, respectively.

By looking at Fig. 19, 15 March seems a more logical candidate for CP1 because, after this day, the HI is dramatically growing till 21 April, so it means this point is discovered by HMMR, HLP, and DPS with a delay. For the CP2 (the boundary point between degradation stage and critical stage trend), HMMR, DPS, and HLP were detected on 8 April, while ST and IRLS were discovered it on 20 April, except the LAE method which recognized this point on 22 March. Another version of this data set is used to validate our results. As discussed before, this data set version is composed of a raw vibration signal recorded for six seconds every day with a 100k sampling rate, see panel (a) in Fig. 20. So it means it has an excellent potential to apply various frequency analyses to do condition monitoring. The envelope analysis is applied for each vibration set, and the result is sequentially plotted in panel (b) of Fig. 20. As it can be seen in panel (b) of Fig. 20 after 14 March, harmonic frequency has appeared, which means the bearing went to the degradation stage. Also, after 22 April, the amplitude of harmonic frequency is dramatically increased, which can be considered CP2. By comparing the results of the segmentation method, it can be found that IRLS and ST methods have the best results for this case.

Figure 19: Changing points detection of wind turbine data set.

Figure 20: Changing points detection wind turbine, (a) raw vibration data, (b) envelope spectrum map.

400 5.4.4. Discussion

The error percentage for detecting changing points in all actual data sets is demonstrated in Fig.21. As we can see in both sub-figures for both CP1 and CP2, the ST method has the lowest percentage error. In contrast, the error percentage for the rest of the methods has fluctuated on different data sets, which can include the fact that considering the non-Gaussian noise distribution improves the process of detecting changing points in long-term condition monitoring data.

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Figure 21: Percentage error for real data sets changing points detection, (a) percentage error for CP1, (b) percentage error for CP2.

6. Conclusions

In the paper, a segmentation problem of long-term degradation (health index) data from SCADA systems has been investigated. The long-term data describes the degradation process. There are several approaches assuming a model of such degradation. Here, we follow the idea of 3 stages with different properties (see Fig. 3). In practical application, it is a really crucial task to detect when a machine is changing its condition from a healthy stage to a degradation stage (warning) and degradation stage to a critical stage (alarm), and it is the base of further analysis like prognostics. Also, in many papers, researchers focus on the last segment, but they don't mention how they have found the division between stages 2 and 3 and whether this detected point coincides with the true start time of the rapid development of the fault in the machine. Therefore, in this paper, we tested various techniques for CPx finding, as CPx is a basis for identifying data segments with different properties. The achievements of this paper can be summarised as follow:

- A model of HI data was proposed as three segments sequence with non-Gaussian noise (student t-distributed) to describe the degradation process, which can be used to simulate the artificial data set.
- Moreover, we showed that the non-Gaussianity of the model makes detection efficiency worse.
- We applied selected methods to simulate and analyse signals with Gaussian and non-Gaussian noise. We used Monte Carlo simulation and box plot-based visualization to provide meaningful results. In the case of Gaussian noise, most of the mentioned methods have almost been able to detect changing points, although a few methods, such as HLP and ST, had the lowest error. However, the situation is entirely different in the presence of non-Gaussian noise. As we expected, the efficacy of methods derived based on Gaussian distribution decreased with the increase in impulsiveness of HI. In contrast, the efficacy of robust methods such as ST, LAE, and IRLS have not been significantly influenced by increasing impulsiveness.
- We have noticed that detection of CP1 is much more difficult than CP2. Statistical properties evolve in time for the whole life of the machine. The difference between the end of stage 1 and the beginning of stage 2 is not so clear as between stage 2 and stage 3, as we change the trend from linear to exponential.

We applied the procedure to real data sets known in the community as benchmark (reference) data sets (namely IMS, FEMTO, and data from wind turbine drive). Additionally, we presented a waterfall plot of envelope spectrum calculated for available raw vibration data for IMS and wind turbine data sets. Such a 3D plot demonstrates how the envelope spectrum changes allow validating visually that detected changing points are correct. Also, the results obtained from applying the mentioned methods to real data sets and comparing them with the results of envelope analysis show that the ST method has the most efficiency in detecting changing points. Furthermore, because the investigated data sets are benchmark data sets, many papers use them as references every year. The researchers can use the results of the real data set section, particularly 3D plots to compare research results.

Also, it is noteworthy that the ST method, developed based on non-Gaussian distribution, had the proper efficiency in detecting changing points in both simulated and real data sets. This can be a point to consider for the researcher working in the field of long-term condition monitoring data analysis in a harsh environment to choose the noise distribution. Although there are other noise distributions to describe impulsive behavior of the degradation process, which may be more compatible with this procedure, this issue deserves more research in the future.

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Conflicts of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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